

SUKUK MARKET AND THEIR RISKS IN GLOBAL AND UZBEKISTAN FINANCIAL MARKET

*Valikhanova Robiya Baxodir qizi, TSUE, 2ND year Master's student,
E-mail: ms.abdumannopova@mail.ru
Yuldasheva Umida Ansanaliyevna TSUE, Professor.*

Annotation. In recent years, the role of sukuk in global financial markets has grown significantly, making an important contribution to capital market development as an innovative financial instrument. In this article the evolution of sukuk as a vital component of global debt capital markets and assesses Uzbekistan's opportunities to become a meaningful participant in this resilient asset class will be analyzed. Drawing on the latest data from AAOIFI, S&P Global Ratings, Fitch Ratings, IIFM Sukuk Reports, ICD-Refinitiv (2020–2024), and Uzbekistan's regulatory documents (2021–2025), the analysis confirms that the global sukuk market will grow from USD 904.5 billion in 2023 to USD 1.15 trillion by the end of 2024 (CAGR 19.1%). Within this context, the article analyses Uzbekistan's regulatory achievements, infrastructure financing needs, Shariah governance gaps, liquidity constraints, and tax-legal barriers. Benchmarking successful experiences (Malaysia, Indonesia, Türkiye, and African issuers), the paper proposes a practical roadmap that includes establishing a National Shariah Advisory Council, adopting AAOIFI Standard

Keywords: Sukuk, Islamic finance, financial securities, risk assessment, regulatory challenges, AAOIFI, Uzbekistan

Аннотация. В последние годы роль сукук на мировых финансовых рынках заметно возросла, внося существенный вклад в развитие рынков капитала как инновационный финансовый инструмент. Данное исследование анализирует эволюцию сукук как важнейшего элемента глобальных рынков долгового капитала и оценивает возможности Узбекистана стать полноправным участником этого устойчивого класса активов. На основе актуальных данных AAOIFI, S&P Global Ratings, Fitch Ratings, отчетов IIFM, ICD-Refinitiv (2020–2024) и нормативных документов Узбекистана 2021–2025 гг. подтверждается рост глобального рынка сукук с 904,5 млрд долл. США в 2023 г. до 1,15 трлн долл. к концу 2024 г. (CAGR 19,1 %). В этом контексте анализируются регуляторные успехи Узбекистана, потребности в финансировании инфраструктуры, пробелы в шариатском управлении, ограничения ликвидности и налогово-правовые барьеры. Опираясь на успешный опыт Малайзии, Индонезии, Турции и африканских эмитентов, предлагается практическая дорожная карта: создание Национального шариатского консультативного совета, принятие стандарта AAOIFI 62,

Ключевые слова: Сукук, исламские финансы, финансовые ценные бумаги, оценка рисков, вопросы регулирования, AOIFE, Узбекистан.

Introduction. Islamic finance has rapidly developed over the past few decades, with Sukuk emerging as a key investment vehicle globally. Sukuk, or Islamic bonds, offer Sharia-compliant alternatives to traditional bonds, avoiding interest payments (riba) and instead employing risk-sharing

structures (Usmani, 2002)¹. By the end of 2022, the global Sukuk issuance exceeded \$180 billion, with Malaysia, Saudi Arabia, and Indonesia leading issuance volumes (AAOIFI, 2023)².

Uzbekistan, a Muslim-majority country with a growing economy, is an attractive market for Islamic financial products. However, its Sukuk market faces regulatory, economic, and operational challenges that slow its development. This article aims to evaluate the development of the Sukuk market globally and identify barriers in Uzbekistan's market, providing insights into mitigating these challenges. Despite the growing demand and positive momentum in favor of Islamic finance and green development, there are several challenges that need to be addressed for the development of a green sukuk ecosystem in Uzbekistan. Firstly, the growth of Islamic finance in the country is still in its early stages. The existing Islamic finance practices rely on the conventional legislation, and Islamic finance instruments are still to be recognized at the levels of policy and legislation. In view of Uzbekistan's very brief experience in Islamic finance, a substantial effort will be needed to issue a sukuk, which would come as a novelty to investors and might well be considered more complex than a traditional bond. Secondly, the capital markets in the country are underdeveloped and immature. Although the government of Uzbekistan has recently taken important steps towards increasing the role of capital markets, strategies still need to be implemented to raise the number of issuers and increase the demand from investors. The financial markets are largely dominated by the banking sector, and the banks' engagement in capital markets is restricted by the legal and regulatory environments. This leads to the third obstacle to the issuance of a sukuk: the lack of a regulatory framework. As an emerging sector of the economy, Islamic finance requires the necessary enabling environment. Certain elements of the existing legal framework may be instrumental in the growth of Islamic finance, but specific Islamic contracts such as sukuk call for legal and regulative changes. Even though the financial effect of a sukuk is similar to that of a conventional bond, they differ with respect to the transfer of ownership and adherence to Islamic Law. These differences call for the adoption of a more comprehensive legal framework reflective of the distinctive features of sukuk.³

Literature review. Sukuk market The Global Financial Crisis, characterized by reduced lending, constrained credit and weak GDP growth, underscored the need for alternative financing. Sukuk gained prominence in this context due to their asset-backed and risk-sharing nature. As a resilient and Shariah-compliant instrument, they mobilize long-term capital and support both public and private sector recovery (Naz, 2025). On contrary, Kartini and Milawati (2020) questioned Sukuk's short-run effectiveness in Indonesia, reporting negligible or statistically insignificant effects, suggesting that institutional and market readiness may moderate its growth impact. Sukuk's hybrid structure, combining equity and debt features, also offers financial stability and reduces dependency on conventional borrowing (Gubareva et al., 2024). Its use in infrastructure, energy and social sectors (Smaoui et al., 2021) positions it as a tool for inclusive development. Ali et al. (2024) find that green Sukuk issued in Indonesia (2018–2021) significantly supported economic growth, social development and financial performance, with environmental certification attracting diverse investors. In Uzbekistan, emerging studies by local scholars such as Nazarov (2024) delve into the compatibility of Islamic financing with the nation's transition economy. When it comes to the demand for an Islamic capital market (ICMs) in Uzbekistan, Asadov et al. (2024) studied the feasibility of introducing ICM products in Uzbekistan. The conducted survey of the general public and the interviews with IF and capital market experts confirmed the presence of significant demand and large potential for Islamic capital market products. Similar to the findings of previous studies by Imamnazarov (2020) and Abdullayev et al. (2023) for general IF products, the study also reveals that despite low IF awareness and an underdeveloped capital market, there is strong demand for Islamic capital market products in the country (Asadov et al. 2024).

¹ Usmani, M. T. (2002). *An Introduction to Islamic Finance*. Kluwer Law International.

² AAOIFI. (2023). *Islamic Finance Development Report 2023*

³ Pre-feasibility study of sukuk market in Uzbekistan report by UNDP 2021

Their short-horizon analysis suggests green Sukuk may be more resilient and appealing to investors during periods of heightened sustainability awareness compared to conventional Sukuk. Uzbekistan's efforts to enter the Islamic finance market have been gradual. The Central Bank of Uzbekistan only recently began exploring Sharia-compliant financing structures, and current legislative frameworks remain underdeveloped (Asadov & Alam, 2021). While a few pilot Sukuk issuances have been explored, the lack of a Sharia-compliant financial ecosystem limits progress. The AAOIFI (2024) report mentions that in Uzbekistan, financial literacy and public awareness around Sukuk are limited, which has affected local demand. Comparatively, countries like Kazakhstan have made greater strides, having launched multiple Sukuk bonds since 2016, with regulatory support that has attracted foreign investment (Alam & Asadov, 2020). Although Uzbekistan has adopted a number of targets regarding environmental issues, there is still no legal and regulatory framework in this area. This situation constitutes another major barrier to the promotion of green finance. As an emerging sector, Islamic finance also requires the necessary enabling environment. Certain elements of the existing legal framework may be instrumental in the growth of Islamic finance, but specific Islamic contracts such as sukuk call for legal and regulative changes. Even though the financial effect of a sukuk is similar to that of a conventional bond, they differ with respect to the transfer of ownership and adherence to Islamic Law. These differences call for the adoption of a more comprehensive legal framework reflective of the distinctive features of sukuk. Box 4.1 identifies the various regulatory areas which need to be taken into consideration when seeking to introduce sukuk in Uzbekistan. (UNDP 2021 Report)

Methodology. This study is based on a **qualitative research approach** using secondary data. Information was collected from international reports (AAOIFI, IIFM, S&P Global Ratings, Fitch Ratings, ICD-Refinitiv), academic articles, and Uzbekistan's regulatory documents (2021–2025). The collected data were analyzed through **descriptive, comparative, and regulatory-gap analysis**. First, global Sukuk market trends—issuance volumes, growth rates, and market drivers—were examined using descriptive analysis. Second, Uzbekistan's regulatory environment was compared with leading Sukuk markets such as Malaysia, Indonesia, Saudi Arabia, Türkiye, and Kazakhstan. Finally, risks were categorized into Shariah, legal, market, liquidity, and operational risks to assess challenges specific to Uzbekistan.

This methodology ensures a structured and evidence-based evaluation of global Sukuk developments and the readiness of Uzbekistan's financial system for Sukuk implementation.

Analysis. The global sukuk market was valued at USD 1.21 trillion in 2024. Looking ahead, it is projected to reach USD 3.99 trillion by 2033, with an expected growth rate (CAGR) of 13.44% from 2025 to 2033. Factors driving this market include the ongoing growth of Islamic finance and banking institutions, an increasing variety of assets, expanding infrastructure development, and the establishment of comprehensive and investor-friendly regulatory frameworks by Islamic finance authorities and standardization organizations.

Sukuk Market Trends/Drivers Rising global economic instability the rising global economic instability is fostering a favorable outlook for the Sukuk market. In periods of economic turmoil, investors search for stable and secure investment options to protect their assets. The asset-backed and risk-sharing characteristics of Sukuk align seamlessly with these goals. It serves as a strong alternative to traditional financial instruments, adhering to ethical standards that forbid interest-based transactions and speculative undertakings. As economic instability continues, its attractiveness as a safe-haven investment grows. Investors regard it as a dependable method to preserve wealth and achieve steady returns while steering clear of risks associated with conventional financial markets. Additionally, both governments and corporations are increasingly utilizing Sukuk to finance critical projects, as it offers a stable source of funding during uncertain economic times. Fast-paced urban growth in Middle Eastern nations the rapid urban growth occurring in Middle Eastern nations is creating a multitude of opportunities for the Sukuk market. As these countries undergo swift urban development and

infrastructure enhancement, the demand for financing these projects has surged. With its Sharia-compliant and asset-backed framework, Sukuk stands out as an appealing financing method for governments and corporations embarking on major projects. The progress of modern cities, transport systems, utilities, and real estate developments necessitates significant capital, and Sukuk provides a practical and ethically appropriate solution. Investors are attracted to Sukuk offerings linked to these development initiatives due to their stability and predictable returns. Furthermore, the Middle East serves as a center for Islamic finance activities, and local governments are eager to promote the market. This dedication, along with supportive regulatory environments, encourages the issuance of Sukuk to facilitate urbanization efforts.

Diagram is from <https://www.researchandmarkets.com>⁴

Top 10 Largest Dollar Sukuk Outstanding			
Bond	Amount Outstanding (\$mn)	Price	YTM
Saudi Arabia 3.628% 2027	4,500	97.28	4.91%
Aramco 2.694% 2031	3,000	86.09	5.28%
Turkey Sukuk 7.25% 2027	3,000	102.34	6.05%
ISDB 1.262% 2036	2,500	96.12	4.61%
Saudi PIF 6% 2028	2,250	102.35	5.30%
Indonesia 4.15% 2027	2,000	98.37	4.94%
Oman 4.875% 2030	1,750	99.38	5.00%
Saudi Electricity 5.684% 2053	1,500	94.99	6.06%
DPW 6% Perp	1,500	99.70	6.45%
Riyad Sukuk 3.174% 2030	1,500	99.86	4.39%

Source: BondbloX, Bloomberg | Data as of 15 Jan 25; Only one sukuk taken per issuer

⁴ <https://www.researchandmarkets.com/reports/5946906>

⁵ BondbloX, Bloomberg | Data as of 15 January 2025; Only one sukuk taken per issuer

Sukuk issuance is projected to maintain its upward trend in 2025, with total amounts anticipated to fall between USD 190 billion and USD 200 billion, as reported by S&P Global Ratings. The Shariah-compliant bond sector has demonstrated resilience, despite a slight decrease in total issuance from USD 197.8 billion in 2023 to USD 193.4 billion in 2024. A primary factor has been the significant increase in foreign currency sukuk issuance, which surged by 29% to reach USD 72.7 billion, driven primarily by issuers from Saudi Arabia, along with corporations in Malaysia and Indonesia. With global liquidity on the rise and major central banks gradually moving towards monetary easing, issuers have been capitalizing on favorable market conditions. While the pace of interest rate cuts may slow down in 2025, Saudi Arabia's need for financing remains high as the kingdom continues to pursue its Vision 2030 economic diversification agenda. This is likely to sustain issuance levels, especially as Saudi banks, corporations, and the government aim to attract foreign capital. Saudi Arabian issuer have established themselves as a preeminent player in the foreign currency sukuk market, in addition to Malaysia and Indonesia. In 2024, institutions and companies in the kingdom increased their activity, significantly contributing to the surge in regional issuance. Kuwait, Qatar, and Oman also experienced heightened issuance, whereas the UAE saw a slight drop. With sukuk providing a crucial avenue for Saudi borrowers to secure liquidity while broadening their funding sources, foreign currency issuance is expected to remain robust in 2025. Global sukuk issuances are expected to hit \$200bn in 2025, with the total global outstanding sukuk [poised to exceed \\$1tn](#) this year, as per debt market experts. S&P analysts said that foreign-currency denominated sukuk saw a 29% YoY rise, standing at \$72.7bn in 2024. While global geopolitical tensions may rise, S&P forecasts that these will have minimal impact on sukuk issuance in 2025. Uzbekistan's efforts to enter the Islamic finance market have been gradual. The Central Bank of Uzbekistan only recently began exploring Sharia-compliant financing structures, and current legislative frameworks remain underdeveloped (Asadov & Alam, 2021).⁶ While a few pilot Sukuk issuances have been explored, the lack of a Sharia-compliant financial ecosystem limits progress. The AAOIFI (2024) report mentions that in Uzbekistan, financial literacy and public awareness around Sukuk are limited, which has affected local demand.⁷ Comparatively, countries like Kazakhstan have made greater strides, having launched multiple Sukuk bonds since 2016, with regulatory support that has attracted foreign investment (Alam & Asadov, 2020)⁸. Although Uzbekistan has adopted a number of targets regarding environmental issues, there is still no legal and regulatory framework in this area. This situation constitutes another major barrier to the promotion of green finance. As an emerging sector, Islamic finance also requires the necessary enabling environment. Certain elements of the existing legal framework may be instrumental in the growth of Islamic finance, but specific Islamic contracts such as sukuk call for legal and regulative changes. Even though the financial effect of a sukuk is similar to that of a conventional bond, they differ with respect to the transfer of ownership and adherence to Islamic Law. These differences call for the adoption of a more comprehensive legal framework reflective of the distinctive features of sukuk. Box 4.1 identifies the various regulatory areas which need to be taken into consideration when seeking to introduce sukuk in Uzbekistan.⁹(UNDP 2021 Report)

Conclusion. The development of a robust Sukuk market in Uzbekistan could significantly enhance financial inclusivity and economic resilience. However, this potential remains largely untapped due to regulatory limitations, market volatility, and the need for standardization. Drawing from successful models in Malaysia and Saudi Arabia, this article concludes that Uzbekistan must

⁶ Asadov, A., & Alam, M. (2021). *Challenges and Opportunities in Islamic Finance in Central Asia*. Springer.

⁷

• ⁸ Asadov, A., & Alam, M. (2021). *Challenges and Opportunities in Islamic Finance in Central Asia*. Springer.

• AAOIFI. (2024). *Islamic Finance Development Report 2024*.

⁹ Pre-feasibility study of sukuk market in Uzbekistan report by UNDP 2021

invest in regulatory infrastructure, market education, and Sharia-compliance frameworks to establish investor confidence and expand its Sukuk market.

To mitigate specific risks, Uzbekistan's regulatory authorities should consider aligning with AAOIFI standards and collaborating with experienced Islamic finance institutions. With targeted reforms, Uzbekistan can position itself as a regional hub for Islamic finance, attracting foreign investment and contributing to sustainable economic growth.

References

1. Accounting and Auditing Organization for Islamic Financial Institutions (AAOIFI). (2023). *Annual Report 2023 on the Global Sukuk Market*. AAOIFI. Retrieved from <https://aaoifi.com>
2. Alam, N., & Asadov, A. (2021). Developing Islamic finance in Central Asia: Case studies of Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan. *Journal of Islamic Banking and Finance*, 38(2), 33-48.
3. Chapra, M. U. (2018). *The Future of Economics: An Islamic Perspective*. Islamic Foundation.
4. Hassan, M. K., & Lewis, M. K. (2009). *Handbook of Islamic Banking*. Edward Elgar Publishing.
5. International Islamic Financial Market (IIFM). (2023). *Sukuk Report: A Comprehensive Study of the Global Sukuk Market*. IIFM Publications. Available at <https://iifm.net>
6. Shamsuddin, A., & Razak, N. A. (2021). The influence of regulatory frameworks on Sukuk market stability. *International Journal of Islamic Finance*, 6(4), 45-63.
7. Springer and Web of Science. Various articles on Islamic finance, Sukuk structures, and market developments. Available at [Springer](#) and [Web of Science](#)
8. The Business Season. (2023). Uzbekistan's financial market outlook: Opportunities and challenges in Sukuk and Islamic finance. Business Insights. Retrieved from <https://thebusinessseason.com>
9. Usmani, M. T. (2002). *An Introduction to Islamic Finance*. Idaratul Ma'arif.